

**22NRM03 “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling
for heavy duty hydrogen transport”**

Report A3.2.1

**Review of existing protocols and guidelines related to the validation of the hydrogen sampling
systems that are used for off-line quality control at HRS.**

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Summary

This review was written as part of activity A3.2.1 from the Partnership on Metrology project “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling for heavy duty hydrogen transport” (MetHyTrucks). The three-year European project started 1st June 2023.

This report summarizes literature and publications on existing protocols and guidelines related to the validation of the hydrogen sampling systems that are used for off-line quality control at HRS, including those developed in EMPIR JRPs 16ENG01 MetroHyVe and 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2, and in other relevant projects. Further, some information has been gathered from users active in the field via a questionnaire sent out by RISE and via email contact.

This report was written by:

Name	Institution	E-Mail
Danique van Workum	VSL	<i>Dvanworkum@vsl.nl</i>
Stefan Persijn	VSL	<i>Spersijn@vsl.nl</i>
Karine Arrhenius	RISE	<i>Karine.arrhenius@ri.se</i>
Maxime DUFOND	ENGIE	<i>Maxime.dufond@engie.com</i>
Etienne BASSET	ENGIE	<i>Etienne.basset@engie.com</i>
Christian Spitta	ZBT	<i>C.spitta@zbt.de</i>
Matz Dietrich	ZBT	<i>M.dietrich@zbt.de</i>
Alexander Kvasnicka	ZBT	<i>A.kvasnicka@zbt.de</i>
Sven Kaiser	ZBT	<i>S.kaiser@zbt.de</i>
Thor Anders Aarhaug	SINTEF	<i>Taarhaug@sintef.no</i>
Thomas Bacquart	NPL	<i>Thomas.bacquart@npl.co.uk</i>

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1 Introduction

Hydrogen is an energy carrier that has been studied in the last two decades to create a more carbon-neutral future. Energy that is generated from sources such as sunlight, water flow, wind or biomass can be stored as hydrogen (from water electrolysis, biomass gasification) and used at a later moment. Hydrogen can be used to generate electricity through a fuel cell system and then power an electrical engine. Due to the low mass of hydrogen, its energy density and ability to be compressed, a large volume of hydrogen can be contained in a reservoir, allowing a heavy-duty vehicle to drive over long distances (i.e., 1000 km) on one tank [1]. The second advantage of hydrogen is that the tank can be rapidly refilled, similar to petrol tanks. For example, a car tank can be fully refilled in approximately 3-5 minutes, or 10-20 minutes for a bus. Therefore, using hydrogen as an energy carrier is particularly interesting for the transportation sector [2]. Hydrogen at hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) is compressed to 35-70 MPa and is used to refuel vehicles via a dispenser [3].

Figure 1 Schematic example of parallel filling of a sample cylinder for hydrogen quality analysis

The quality of the hydrogen fuel may have a direct effect on the fuel cell electrical vehicle performance, especially ultra traces of sulphur may deteriorate performance or reduce the lifetime of the system. Heavy duty transportation is an extremely cost-efficient sector of the industry and vehicle lifetime is cornerstone of the business model. Therefore the impact of low-quality hydrogen fuel may be extremely detrimental to the transport business and hinder the deployment of this low carbon solution for heavy duty transport. International standards such as ISO 14687 [4] or EN17124 [5] define specific thresholds for a large range of chemical compounds in hydrogen fuel. To assure that the level of contaminants in hydrogen fuel dispensed at HRS is below the threshold specified in ISO 14687, sampling is performed before analysis. To be accurately executed, sampling should be done via validated sampling devices using standardized protocols. Currently, there is a lack of validated sampling devices for heavy duty (HD) HRS sampling, and besides ASTM D7606 [6], standardized validation protocols do not exist.

Different sampling systems have been developed to sample at light duty (LD) HRS, the most recent overview is found in Review Report A1.1.2 of this project. Since almost all studies so far have been focused on LD and not on HD, the information in this review will also be based mostly on LD sampling systems. All companies that operate sampling systems for HRS have their own protocols in place for operations. During research projects like 16ENG01 MetroHyVe and 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2 these have been investigated and combined into good practice guides. This review will summarize the literature and guides that have been published so far in relation to the validation of sampling systems for the off-line quality control of LD- and HD-HRS.

Contamination found in a hydrogen sample can originate from 3 sources:

- **Hydrogen source**

The probability of occurrence of ISO 14687-2 contaminants in hydrogen depends on the production process [7].

- **Hydrogen refuelling station**

HRS sampling and analysis are not widely applied yet, which makes it difficult to recognize HRS issues, such as compressor oil leakage or an insufficient purge after maintenance [8]. In the HYRAITE D5.1 report, information from stakeholders and from literature were combined to report impurities that could be introduced during sampling. For example, built-in components such as seals, filters and valves could undergo abrasion by particulates. Besides, maintenance can cause pollution of the hydrogen that is sampled. Insufficient cleaning and purging after maintenance introduces oxygen, nitrogen and particulates, while insufficient drying introduces water in the piping. Water can easily adsorb onto the surface and remain in the gas during the purging cycles. Furthermore, residues of lubricant and detergents from maintenance can introduce different poisonous ingredients such as carbon dioxide, sulphur compounds and acetone, causing performance drop or poisoning of the catalyst.

- **Sampling**

Sampling is one of biggest measurement challenges [9]. It is important to differentiate between the sampling system itself and the cylinder used for storing the hydrogen sample. Most sampling systems can be combined with a number of different types of cylinders (e.g., cylinder connection, water volume, single or double-ended, and most importantly for reactive impurities: the cylinder treatment). Having a good sampling system but using a cylinder which is not suitable for a specific contaminant will lead to an unreliable result. If the sampling procedure is not correctly performed, it may lead to false positives or false negatives. To prevent this, every step should be performed with validated procedures.

It should also be noted that for some of the reactive compounds listed in ISO 14687, only very limited results have been described in literature. The reported absence of such impurities in the H₂ samples does not provide full evidence that it is absent in the H₂ used for refuelling.

The sampling exercise involves different aspects/steps which are summarized below, all of these steps should be included in a sampling protocol:

- Organisation of the sampling
 - 1) Permissions
 - 2) Risk assessment
- The sampling system including the sampling methodology (often referred to as parallel or series)
 - 1) Procedure to prepare the sampling system before sampling
 - 2) Connection to the station
 - 3) Sampling
 - 4) Procedure for the depressurization of the device (often after sampling) and disconnection

5) Control of the station

- The sampling vessel
 - 1) Selection of material, material treatment, size and configuration (1 or 2 valves)
 - 2) Procedure to prepare the cylinder before sampling (including purging, time aspect – how long time after preparation the cylinder can be used)
 - 3) Filling pressure / size of the sample
 - 4) Disconnection
 - 5) Transportation back to the laboratory
- Representativeness of the sample
 - 1) Is the entire target population available for sample collection: sample from different storage banks?
- For particles:
 - 1) Selection of the filters (pore size...)
 - 2) Procedure to prepare the filters

A validated protocol or guideline is missing for most of these steps, so only the aspects with developments in this area are discussed. A questionnaire with 12 questions was sent to 8 stakeholders or project partners in order to collect information on current practices regarding different steps of the sampling strategies and protocols used for these steps. 6 replies were received.

2 Standardization of sampling

ISO 14687:2019 describes the 13 gaseous contaminants which, together with particulates, must be monitored in hydrogen fuel to be below the specified threshold [4]. Hydrogen used for fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEV) should meet these requirements. If these requirements cannot be met, the proton exchange membranes in fuel cells could be damaged and the process of conversion to hydrogen fuel technologies in the transportation sector will be slowed down [10]. Therefore, it is mandatory to ensure accurate measurement of impurities.

To get an accurate measurement of impurities, two processes should be carried out carefully: sampling at the nozzle and gas quality testing. Much is known about how different impurities can be measured (typically several different instruments are needed to cover the full range of analytes) and about what materials to use during sampling with new information recently published as part of MetroHyVe2 project. However, not much is published yet on validation of sampling systems, since many users operate their own sampling system with lack of intercomparisons, standardized protocols and methods, or access to reference materials. Annex K of ISO 19880-1:2020 describes sampling procedures [11]. This is an informative annex to the standard, which means that the sampling is not standardized yet. A normative document, ISO/DIS 19880-9 is currently under development and is expected to be published in 2024. Different methodologies are described on how to collect samples

from the dispenser nozzle, on which more information can be found in the review of A1.1.2 of the MetHyTrucks project.

In the United States of America, sampling at HRS is standardized in ASTM D7606 [6]. The standard practice is developed for sampling with a hydrogen quality sampling apparatus (HQSA) at 35 or 70 MPa, but is only applicable to sampling and not to the corresponding analysis. ASTM D7650 and D7651 describe sampling and analysis of particulates. This standard will also be under revision to harmonize with ISO 19880-9 and to include heavy duty sampling.

3 Organisation of the sampling

3.1 Permissions

Permission for sampling is normally obtained from the HRS operator. In some cases, safety training is a requirement before getting access. This training can be provided by the operator.

ZBT follows the Shell Retail Permit-to-Work system: the operators of the HySam device at ZBT get regular trainings on how to work safely at a refuelling station. The samplings at the HRS are only operated by employees with valid certificates. In addition to that, ZBT asks for a Permit-to-Work from the HRS operator on-site before starting the sampling.

3.2 Risk assessment

Some participants of the questionnaire perform a risk assessment before each sampling occasion and some do not. Documentation of the sampling strategy and adapter used is also a requirement, and used as part of the risk assessment.

There is a comprehensive hazard assessment for the HySam device including operating instructions, safety consideration, Ex protection documentation, FMEA etc. – this is the basis for safe operation of the sampling device. In addition to that, ZBT clarifies the local and technical circumstances of the HRS. When there is a cooperation with a new HRS operator or site, in preparation of the sampling ZBT is asking to fill out a form with questions regarding safety aspects like grounding, venting etc.

3.3 Shipping of dangerous goods: cylinders

Before and after sampling, cylinders should be transported (from/to the laboratory). All gases are automatically classified in Class 2 according to the Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road (ADR) [13]. Dependent on the filling of a sampling cylinder, it classifies as a class 2.1, 2.2 or 2.3. Not only according to the ADR, but also to the International Regulations Concerning the Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Rail (RID), International Maritime Dangerous Goods (IMDG) and the International Air Transport Association (IATA), hydrogen is classified as dangerous. Handling of hydrogen induces hazards like fire, explosion and pressure. When transporting the sampling cylinders, all parties in the logistic chain should take their responsibility and take into account the safety measures. Therefore, during transportation, the correct hazard labels for flammable gas and compressed gas should be applied. More information can be found in Deliverable 7 of the MetroHyVe 2 project [14].

4 The sampling system including the sampling methodology

4.1 Procedure to prepare the sampling system before sampling

Not all companies participating in the questionnaire prepared the sampling system. The ones that do have a protocol for preparing the sampling system prepare it by purging it with nitrogen and/or hydrogen. Furthermore, some participants check the system (tightness of the device, valves, etc.) before sampling.

4.2 Connection to and control of the station

From the questionnaire, it was seen that there are many different systems and protocols in place. From the six participants, one uses a serial sampling system, three use a parallel sampling system and two are using multiple systems (direct and parallel, serial and parallel). The participants indicate to sample at the nozzle/receptacle.

Some participants of the questionnaire monitor flow and/or pressure, but most of the participants do not.

4.3 Sampling

Different sampling protocols are mentioned in the questionnaire answers, among which are the ASTM D7606 standard practice and the J2601 protocol. However, almost all participants have their own internal protocols for sampling.

4.4 Procedure for the venting of the device

Most of the participants use a (mobile) device which vents at a height of 3 m through a 10 m stainless steel flexible hose (often after sampling and disconnection). Another protocol mentioned in the questionnaire is based on depressurization to air.

5 The sampling vessel

5.1 Selection of material, material treatment, size and valve configuration

One of the restrictive parameters is the vessel compatibility with the chosen sampling device [15]. Different devices can be connected to only a certain set of vessels. Furthermore, several of the contaminants listed in ISO 14687 are reactive and might therefore adsorb onto the cylinder wall. If losses occur during sampling or transportation, this will lead to falsely lower contaminant concentrations. Therefore, passivated cylinders should be used to store these impurities. For representative sampling, the low-level contaminants should be retained in the cylinder for at least a few months [16]. This agrees with what is stated in ISO 19880-1, Annex K [11]. However, the short MetroHyVe 1 stability study was not conclusive on whether aluminium or stainless-steel cylinders

should be used, and which treatment is best. Especially HCl and H₂S were seen to have stability issues in the cylinders, as such reactive compounds are known to interact with the cylinder surface [15].

A MetroHyVe 2 study was designed to gain more insight into the cylinder treatments [16]. The reactive compounds formic acid, formaldehyde, hydrogen sulphide and hydrogen chloride were tested at 2× the ISO threshold, ammonia at 4× the ISO threshold and water at the ISO threshold (best approach would be actually to perform at the threshold level for all compounds, but this can be analytically challenging for some compounds). Compared to a previous study, the stability of the more reactive compounds was studied for new cylinder types and treatments. Also the effect of ‘moist’ (~5 ppm H₂O) versus ‘dry’ (<< 5 ppm H₂O) was studied. Most cylinders tested are suitable for some of the compounds, but not all. The DB Gold cylinder from EffecTech showed good performance for nearly all tested reactive compounds, except for OCS and for total sulphur components an increase was observed in this type of cylinder. DB Gold also seems to give an increase in formaldehyde concentration for dry H₂, which could be potentially lead to false positives and a loss for formic acid (e.g., 25% after 10 days for ‘dry’ H₂) which could lead to false negatives. For ‘moist’ H₂, both components were more stable in DB Gold. Sulfinert coated stainless steel was also good for most compounds except HCl while for total sulphur and H₂S only for short periods (1-2 months). It should be taken into account that the stability due to cross-reactivity was not studied. It was also seen in this study that the age and history of the cylinder are critical to its performance. Cylinder lifetime and use (e.g., repetitive sampling) should be monitored, and if needed, performance should be evaluated after use.

During MetroHyVe 2, a report was written on the different valves used on sampling cylinders for hydrogen sampling [17]. Based on feedback from end-users, it is known that diaphragm and needle valves are the most used. Most valves can be passivated, as is advised. ISO 19880-1, Annex K states to use valves made of stainless steel and not brass [11]. Not much is known about the dead volumes of the valves [17]. More research should be done on this subject, as it might influence the stability or composition of the sampled gas. Furthermore, research on the difference in performance between passivated and non-passivated valves is also lacking.

The best sampling containers for HD-HRS sampling are expected to be similar to those for LD-HRS sampling.

5.2 Procedure to prepare the cylinder before sampling

Purging procedures are mentioned in ASTM D7606 and ISO19880-1, but currently there is no standard procedure. An extensive purging procedure should be used to avoid false positives of, for example, air contamination [15]. According to ISO 19880-1, Annex K, vessels should be cleaned by either purging with high purity H₂ or evacuation, typically to 10⁻⁵ MPa [11]. ASTM D7606 specifies that the HQSA and sampling vessel should be flushed by purging ten times at a flow of 33.3 g/s [14]. Furthermore, two or three sample cylinders should be collected to compare representativeness and prove the existence of a certain contaminant. This purge procedure cannot be applied to single-ended cylinders, so in the HyCoRA project an alternative procedure was developed by SINTEF, in which the cylinder should be evacuated and pressurized repeatedly three times. The cylinders should then be evacuated again before sampling. This procedure was, however, not evaluated with respect to the pressure levels and repeat cycles, nonetheless there were no signs of carry-over. NPL also developed a purging procedure, during which they use a so-called ‘evacuation rig’ consisting of a roughing pump, turbo pump and

residual gas analysis. It was shown that the residual water content was 200 nmol/mol [14]. Water is fairly difficult to remove from the sampling device/cylinder through purging.

All participants from the questionnaire responded that they have their own protocol in place for preparation of the cylinder or that they are using the cylinder evacuation protocol from the MetroHyVe study. The protocols are often a combination of repeated evacuation and flushing/purging with either nitrogen or hydrogen.

The MetroHyVe 1 project included a method to fill the cylinder with around 2 bar of Ultra High Purity (UHP) hydrogen before storage and transportation, which poses the advantage that air is less likely to ingress into the cylinder, and the hydrogen can be used to remove air present in the dead volume between the cylinder and apparatus. The analytical result must be corrected for the dilution. During the MetroHyVe 2 project, three methodologies were successfully realized.

5.3 Filling pressure / size of the sample

The filling pressure and size of the sample differ greatly among the participants in the questionnaire. Cylinders of 1 L, 2 L and 10 L are mentioned with pressures between 30-100 bar. The total hydrogen volume therefore varies between 60 L and 1000 L.

5.4 Disconnection

Disconnection requires the sampling device to be depressurized. There are several strategies for this, e.g., use of a bleed valve or depressurization through dispenser for H70.

There is not much to be considered while using the HySam device. The cylinder is closed at the valve on the cylinder when the target pressure is reached. After that, the pressure inside the pipes gets released by opening a valve and releasing the gas over the vent. When atmospheric pressure is reached, the connection hose to the cylinder can be separated and the cylinder can be transported.

5.5 Transportation back to the laboratory

During transportation, contamination of the sample should be avoided and changes (e.g., temperature) to the sample should be minimized [14]. Procedures are necessary for collection, transport and storage to maintain the integrity of the collected sample. The sampling cylinder should be appropriately marked, since hydrogen is classified as dangerous to transport. If the sampling cylinder has a leak, a new sample should be taken.

6 Representativeness of the sample

Samples taken with a parallel sampling system are thought to be representative of the hydrogen fuel delivered to a FCEV, because sampling follows the refuelling protocol [18]. With such a system, no information is obtained about the hydrogen quality in a single storage bank but it can be from several banks. For sampling with a serial sampling system, the HRS should be put in maintenance mode. In this case, hydrogen from only one storage bank can be sampled. If there are multiple storage banks present, multiple samplings should be performed. Consideration should be given to whether one

prefers a sample from a particular storage bank or a more representative fuel sample. Most participants in the questionnaire do not sample from different storage banks.

7 Particulate matter

For particulate matter, two different methods of sampling can be applied. In the first method, the particulates are sampled from the nozzle of the HRS without FCEV as sink. In this case, the HRS has to operate in manual mode with a set flow and pressure during the sampling. In the second method, particulates are sampled from the nozzle of the HRS when a FCEV filling is performed. Then, the HRS is operating normally with the particulate filter inserted between the nozzle and the FCEV receptacle [19].

Within MetroHyVE a good practice guide for the handling, transporting and weighing of filters from particulate sampling in gaseous hydrogen was prepared [20]. A major advantage of using this guide is the fact that it meets with the requirements for filter storage; conditioning and weighing that are laid out in the ambient air standard EN 12341:2014 (although in ambient air particulate mass is normally higher than in hydrogen where the threshold level is 1 mg/kg of H₂).

7.1 Selection of the filters

Recommended filter types are dependent on the instrument manufacturers and providers of sampling equipment. Typical filters are PTFE or porous type (latter were recommended in [20]). There was no significant difference between use of 0.2 and 5 µm filters, both having an efficiency of 99.8% or higher [19].

7.2 Procedure to prepare the filters

The participants from the questionnaire that perform particulate sampling follow ASTM D7650 and D7651. ENGIE uses the HYDAC device and follows the supplier recommendations.

Filter preparation for ASTM and HYDAC strategies for particulate sampling are different, and no direct comparison between methods have been performed [19].

7.3 Further work needed

As seen from public data and work done in the MetroHyVe 2 project, there is still a challenge with gravimetric analysis of filters. Future validation studies should investigate the effect of parameters like the presence of pressure regulator or sampling flow rate that could influence the particulate sampling [19].

8 Performance testing of sampling systems and yield of recovery

To test the yield of recovery of sampling systems and determine challenges regarding material adsorption, purging, and other parameters leading to inaccurate sampling, it is necessary that suitable calibration gases are available. During MetroHyVe 2, a study was conducted on binary calibrants and existing gaps [21]. From a survey, it was concluded that binary calibrants of ammonia, formaldehyde

and formic acid are often not available or show instability. Through the project, novel ammonia and formaldehyde binary calibration gases were tested over 1 year and suitable.

The realisation of certified reference materials for all compounds including reactive gases was challenging. A study by Morris et al. concluded that new cylinder types (other than SPECTRA-SEAL® and aluminium cylinders) are required for samples containing all components to remain stable during transport and analysis [22]. The same study identified that ammonia and formaldehyde or formic acid can't be present in the same cylinder. While calibrants in hydrogen or methane, oxygen, helium, nitrogen, argon, carbon dioxide are widely available among the participants, developments are still necessary in the field of halogenated compounds and sulphur calibrants [21].

9 Sampling inter-comparisons

Bacquart et al. published a study in 2021 where two sampling systems were compared: the H₂ Qualitizer developed by Linde and Air Liquide's H₂ sampling system [12]. This study is the first comparison between two laboratories on the topic of hydrogen fuel according to ISO 14687:2019. Results of Air Liquide and NPL's laboratories were in agreement on the concentrations of seven different contaminants in a pre-made reference material. Results on O₂ and H₂O were diverging, but these concentrations were nonetheless below the ISO 14687 threshold. The diverging results for the H₂O measurement are explained by systematic analytical differences linked to different analytical methods and gas calibrants. Since low fraction reference materials were not available close to the detection limit, an accurate assessment was not possible.

For a second interlaboratory comparison with two samples taken with less than 30 minutes difference by the H₂ sampling system, the analytical results of Air Liquide and NPL agreed for all compounds at 95% confidence level [12]. The only exceptions are nitrogen and again oxygen. The latter one could be explained by the lack of reference materials and the estimation of the limit of detection. The difference in nitrogen levels was explained by the time of sampling in combination with remnants from purging. A decrease in nitrogen concentration was seen over time after purging. Online analysis might be incorporated to assess the presence of oxygen, nitrogen and H₂O during sampling. When comparing the Air Liquide H₂ sampling system with the H₂ Qualitizer, it was seen that both strategies gave equivalent results. The conclusion of this study was that the two systems are equivalent, but more research is needed to gather more data on the different sampling systems. In 2020, a protocol to sample with the H₂ Qualitizer rig was published by Bacquart et al. [23]. They showed that the H₂ Qualitizer is capable of sampling without substantial air or water contamination.

Another study has been performed on comparability between sampling at the HRS nozzle and sampling from a FCEV tank [24]. Sampling at the HRS nozzle was performed with a H₂ Qualitizer system and sampling from the FCEV tank was done with a FCEV sampling rig. Except for the water contaminant, no differences were observed between the two samples and therefore the performance was equivalent.

10 Development of ISO/DIS 19880-9

Currently, ISO/DIS 19880-9, Gaseous hydrogen — Fuelling stations — Part 9: Sampling procedures and hardware for hydrogen fuel quality analysis, is in development [25]. Section 5.2 of ISO/DIS 19880-9 describes that a sample should be collected at a pressure and flow representative for the hydrogen

fuel dispensed. Besides, the sample should be representative for the refuelling protocol that is normally exhibited. For sampling at HD-HRS, this typically translates to 35 MPa of pressure and up to 120 g/s of flow, but could involve up to 70 MPa of pressure and 300 g/s of flow. Furthermore, a sample should be taken from different hydrogen storage banks at the fuelling station. There are also requirements for the HQSA and hydrogen particulate sampling apparatus (HPSA) stated. The hydrogen delivered to the vehicle should be within a temperature range of -40 °C to +50 °C, the apparatus should have a specified cycle life before replacement and all components should be rated for the maximum hydrogen flow. Both the fuelling nozzle and receptacle should be compliant with ISO 17268. Components (such as a cylinder) which are rated lower than the dispensing system maximum allowable working pressure should be placed after a pressure relief device compliant with ISO 4126-1 or ISO 4126-2.

11 Uncertainty estimation

To assess different sampling protocols, the uncertainty of different contributions must be taking into account. These include for example the uncertainty of the reference materials, the uncertainty of the method of analysis but also the uncertainty due to the sampling procedure followed. An extensive guide from Eurachem is available with information on uncertainty estimation for sampling [26]. In this guide, it is mentioned that uncertainties come from different sources, among which heterogeneity, temperature and pressure effects, adsorption in sampling system and transportation and preservation of the sample. To minimize the total uncertainty during sampling, attention must be paid to these activities.

12 Validation of HD-HRS sampling systems

The preparation of the H₂ samples requires considerable expertise and an understanding of the current challenges including representativeness, compatibility, timeliness, safety, environmental conditions, reliability and cost [26]. Here the focus will be mainly on the representativeness of the sample. Whether or not a sample will be representative is determined by several factors:

- I. Sampling system
- II. Sampling container
- III. Sampling procedure
- IV. Sample handling (temperature during transport and storage, storage period)

If any of these links is weak, then the sample will not be representative of the H₂ quality at the refuelling nozzle. It is common to underestimate the influence that the collection of samples has on the measurement variance [32].

For LD-HRS sampling applications, many different sampling systems are currently in use and more systems will likely be added in the near future. For HD-HRS sampling, a similar development is anticipated. It is crucial for users of such sampling systems to know if the sampling system can be used to obtain representative samples of H₂. Use of an unvalidated sampling system can lead to false positives ('good hydrogen' being classified as non-compliant) or false negatives ('bad hydrogen' is not detected and used to fuel cars), both cases may lead to economic damage for the end-users.

Therefore, a proper validation of sampling systems is needed to provide (potential) users of these systems information on their reliability. Part of the validation should include reactive compounds (in particular sulphurs, halogenates, formic acid, and ammonia), moisture and particulates since these are thought to be most prone to be affected by the sampling system (false positive and negative).

Due to limited information on the validation of HRS sampling systems, some recommendations on how to perform such a validation are presented.

An important limitation of field validation is that the hydrogen quality at the nozzle is often really good and thus no contaminants are detected. Therefore, this approach may limit the ability for recognizing false negatives. Secondly, a repeatability study in field validation can be affected by the HRS operation, where the delivery is based on the different storage banks, change of environmental conditions and the time after HRS maintenance which may influence the hydrogen fuel composition and add variability parameters in the study.

12.1 Metrological approach

To do a proper validation, it is necessary to have a standard method. Based on the method and protocol associated, the sampling users should have a good knowledge of the variability parameters (i.e., impact of pressure, flow), requirements (i.e., stability of the sample in the gas cylinder) and different uncertainty contributions. These parameters will be different for each impurity.

For the realisation of the study, it is critical to have robust analytical system to accurately determine the difference between the samples obtained and to have a reliable source of test gases (i.e., primary reference materials from NMI/DI, accurate and traceable analysis of test gases). Only when the uncertainty contributions of the analytical method, the reference material, typical variation between sample containers, et cetera are known, then a proper validation of a HRS sampling system can be carried out.

Knowledge of the influence of different variables is ideally required before a validation study is executed. Figure 2 shows examples for gasoline sampling on the influence different variables on a specific parameter (taken from [33]).

Figure 2 Example of a study in which the effect of different variables was determined on a physical parameter (here vapour pressure) of gasoline samples. Taken from reference [33].

12.2 Recommended steps to validate a sampling system

- 1) **Ensure the sampling method is well documented, sufficiently tested, and applicable to the end-user's case.** The sampling system, sampling container, sampling procedure and sample handling (requirement for transport) should be clearly defined.
- 2) **Laboratory tests using both contaminated hydrogen and high-purity hydrogen.**
 As a contaminated H₂ source, certified reference gas standards in hydrogen matrix should be used (including at least moisture and at least one or more reactive impurities such as hydrogen sulphide). An alternative may be to use high-purity H₂, (5.0 or better) cylinders to investigate false positive (i.e., air ingress and water presence or insufficient purging). The results when using the sampling system and direct measurements from both cylinders should be compared; these should agree within the measurement uncertainty at 95% confidence level. From such tests, useful information can be obtained, like the minimum flushing volume and the typical variations in analysis results under well-controlled conditions. Secondly, it will inform if the inner surface of the sampling system is not adsorbing reactive compounds and therefore leading to false negative. Such realisation is challenging however, due to the volume of reference gas required. For example, the ASTM D7606 requires to vent 1 kg of hydrogen before sampling, which represents approximately 15 cylinders of 10L filled at 100 bar.
- 3) **Repeated sampling at an HRS from the same H₂ bank**

Repeated sampling from the same storage bank will help to determine the typical variance of the results for the different impurities. Contributions to this spread are due to the sampling system, used sampling containers, analysis, and the operator. A minimum of three samples needs to be taken. As the variance between three samples may be related to the HRS infrastructure, it is important to understand the impact of the HRS infrastructure with regard to the variance of the sampling realisation.

To discriminate between the HRS variation and the sampling system variation, it would be recommended to repeat three samples at two different HRS by the same system and operators. This is relatively challenging due to the logistics associated (i.e., for parallel approach, three FCEV need to be present), access to HRS and availability of HRS (i.e., performing more tests will reduce the overall availability for end users), absence of contaminants in the hydrogen fuel. Such realisation on commercial HRS revealed several technical, logistic and commercial challenges.

4) Comparison with other sampling systems

Several recent comparisons on LD-HRS sampling systems have been carried out [18][29][30][31]. Comparison between unvalidated sampling systems can prove equivalence, it can also help pinpoint issues between sampling systems or sampling procedures. Such realisations are critical to find consensus and identify challenges or better practices.

The realisation of inter-sampling comparisons and agreement between sampling systems would enable evaluation of new sampling systems against a reference or recognised system. Performing a comparison with a validated sampling system can provide direct proof of the validity of the sampling system for those impurities that are present above the limit of quantification of the analytical method.

The complexity of inter-sampling comparisons was highlighted by a MetroHyVe 2 project identifying HRS parameters being a source of variance between sampling system realisations. Therefore it required appropriate control over the HRS while maintaining a low level of contaminants, to obtain equivalence for all the contaminants.

In all steps, all samples need to be analyzed in repeatable conditions within the shortest period of time, specified by the sampling system owner.

Still, performing all the steps described above requires multiple measurements, facilities and reference materials, which leads to a limited number of organizations being able to fully realise it. Deploying service enabling all commercial laboratories to validate their sampling approach would be preferable. Despite the approach proposed above being feasible today, it may not be the most appropriate and metrological approach for the long term. It actually suffers from challenges associated with accessing affordable certified reference materials (step 1), accessing commercial HRS (step 2) and logistical challenges for inter-sampling comparisons (step 3).

In the ideal case, it is recommended for future experiments to develop an HRS able to realise steps 1-3 at the same time. This HRS would be able to be fed with contaminated hydrogen. The concept was investigated within the framework of the MetroHyVe 1 project but technical and financial challenges

made it not feasible at this point in time. Ideally, the system should be fed with all trace contaminants at least 3 levels: below, at, and above the ISO 14687 threshold levels. All contaminants would need to be monitored and certified in hydrogen fuel. Such a system would help validation of sampling systems, sampling procedures and sampling containers. However, such realisation at an HRS level has never been done and would require significant steps to ensure metrological and accurate realisation within the volume and pressure associated and safety of the experiment.

Sampling containers have been extensively studied in MetroHyVe 2, the approach proposed and the results obtained may be suitable to validate the sampling containers. Additional studies may be required to evaluate the impact of environmental conditions during transport (i.e., temperature).

Note that successful validation just shows that a sampling system is performing well at one point in time. Sampling systems need to be well-maintained and regularly inspected to guarantee proper operation in the long term. It would be advised to repeat the validation study after a certain period (e.g., 2 years) to see if similar results are obtained with an 'aged' system.

13 Conclusions

Some studies have been performed on the materials used for the vessels and valves, sampling systems and purging, but most of the reports so far are not completely conclusive. Furthermore, only few laboratory intercomparisons have been published and sampling systems are rarely compared to each other in terms of performance. To validate the sampling systems, HRS hydrogen fuel should be sampled and analysed by different laboratories with their corresponding sampling systems and different analytical techniques. More intercomparison studies are necessary for assessment of sampling systems performance. In literature, deviation of impurity concentrations from expected concentrations is often caused by instability of the component, lack of reference materials for analysis or levels being too close to the limit of detection, the use of different analytical techniques to assess the purity or insufficient purging after maintenance. Standardized, detailed procedures are therefore necessary for contamination-free sampling.

In the few studies that have been performed on the validation of sampling systems, follow-up research was conducted on components that were found to be above the maximum threshold according to ISO 14687:2019. The laboratories were performing their research on the samples that were delivered to the laboratory. However, no validation procedures were in place to investigate whether components could have 'escaped' or adsorbed onto the tubing or cylinder wall during sampling. In other words, if the impurity concentration measured is representative for the storage bank or if a false negative is measured. Therefore, these studies mainly focused on the assessment of false positives. If the sampling is not performing properly, the sample composition could have changed. The HRS then seems to be operating fine and to be compliant with ISO 14687, but it is actually providing vehicles with hydrogen containing too high levels of impurities. Thorough testing of sampling systems is necessary to set up validation and write good practice guides, to prevent false negatives.

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